

MAPWORMS

Mimicking Adaptation
and Plasticity in
WORMS

D4.4 IMMOBILIZED STIMULI- RESPONSIVE HYDROGELS ON SURFACES - UPDATE

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1 INTRODUCTION

The MAPWORMS project aims at the development of novel robot concepts inspired by marine worms and, specifically, to emulate their shape-morphing abilities, **Error! Reference source not found.** Within this framework, Sipuncula, a class of unsegmented marine Annelida worms, serve as the primary source of bioinspiration for designing the final robots, thanks to their straightforward yet effective morphological structure, **Error! Reference source not found.** **A.** This structure enables impressive deformations of their shape and the ability to protrude part of their bodies. In the final robots, these abilities are to be mimicked by combining synthetic hybrid actuation units, **Figure 1B, Panel I**, into a smart and modular architecture capable of responding to various stimuli **Error! Reference source not found.** **B, Panel II.**

Figure 1. (A) Body parts of Sipuncula worms, which have been selected as the main source of bioinspiration for the design of the final robots to be developed within the project. (B). Design concept of the worm-inspired robot. Panel I- Example of an actuation unit including a conductive layer, on which active layers are immobilized. Panel II - The final robots will feature a smart, modular architecture that combines actuation units capable of responding to different stimuli.

Specifically, the project's design goal is to create a worm-inspired soft robot featuring multiple actuation units, each capable of performing simple, primitive movements or functions. In each actuation unit, stiffness variations and internal stress differences triggered by magnetic field, temperature, or pH variations, as well as light stimulation and chemical reactions, enable triggered movement. These actuation units can be combined into more complex structures to achieve sophisticated motion and behaviors inspired by worms, and exploitable in different application scenarios. As in the biological counterpart, the combination of these actuation units aims to activate fluidic transmission mechanisms,

utilizing active and passive structural elements to achieve different mechanical functionalities. As outlined in **Figure 1, Panel I**, some possible actuation unit configurations could include several layers of different compositions. Furthermore, activation of the gel in the hybrid structures by electrochemical stimuli through the surface layer could broaden the trigger diversity of the final robotic systems. Thus, hybrid constructs of solid support and gel structures demonstrating stimuli-responsive properties and their applications are aimed. Toward this goal, the HUJI team developed surface-immobilized stimuli-responsive active gels of different scales on several types of supports.

In this context, this Deliverable 4.4 – “*Immobilized stimuli-responsive hydrogels on surfaces-update*” outlines the progress achieved during the period following the initial 27 months of the project (First reporting period, D4.2), in developing methods to fabricate firm stimuli-responsive hydrogels on surfaces. Specifically, the report provides a summary of the research efforts and introduces current research activities.

2 BACKGROUND AND PAST ACHIEVEMENTS WITHIN THE MAPWORM PROJECT

The research activities within WP4 addressed two major goals: (i) the development of new concepts and methods to design bulk stimuli-responsive hydrogels, while identifying possible applications of these gels for controlled-release, shape-morphing, and self-healing. (ii) development of methodologies to integrate different stimuli-responsive gels with surfaces and identifying possible applications of these gel-modified surfaces. Along the MAPWORMS project, HUJI has continuously adopted an approach in which bulk stimuli-responsive gels and their applications are accompanied by the development of hybrid surface-confined gels and their applications. The results accomplished within these efforts during previous project periods are shortly summarized in this chapter.

2.1 STIMULI-RESPONSIVE DNA-BASED HYDROGELS ON SURFACES FOR SWITCHABLE BIOELECTROCATALYSIS AND CONTROLLED RELEASE OF LOADS

pH-responsive DNA-based hydrogel matrices loaded with different loads were integrated with Au-coated electrode supports and implemented as functional gels for electro-modulated biocatalyzed release of loads from the gels. By the integration of glucose oxidase (**GOx**) into the pH-responsive hydrogel and modifying the gel frameworks with ferrocene (**Fc**) electron-transfer mediating relies, the bioelectrocatalyzed aerobic oxidation of glucose to gluconic acid and acidification of the gel frameworks were demonstrated, **Figure 2(A)**. The acidification process led to hydrogel frameworks with lower stiffness and the dose-controlled release of loads. By switchable ON/OFF activation of bioelectrocatalytic processes, switchable release of loads from the surface-confined hydrogels was demonstrated, **Figure 2(B)**. Different loads, such as fluorophore-modified dextran or fluorophore-labeled insulin, were released from the hydrogel frameworks.

Figure 2. (A) Schematic assembly of a pH-responsive DNA-based hydrogel on an Au-coated electrode surface and its switchable stiffness properties, triggered by pH, enzyme substrate, or potential. (B) Switchable bioelectrocatalytic release of Insulin from the surface-immobilized hydrogel.

The results were reported in detail in deliverable D4.2 **and published as an open-access research paper in *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 15, 37011-37025, 2023**, acknowledging the MAPWORMS European project, 101046846.^[1]

2.2 REDOX-RESPONSIVE CARBOXYMETHYL CELLULOSE TRANSIENT DISSIPATIVE BULK CRYOGELS

The subsequent interim research activities of WP4 within the MAPWORM project included the development of transient redox-active stiffness-switchable cryogels. Within these efforts, a general method for controlling the switchable, dynamic stiffness properties of gels was developed, **Figure 3**. Polysaccharides such as carboxymethyl cellulose (**CMC**) were crosslinked by redox-active Fe³⁺-tricarboxylate bridging units to form higher-stiffness state gel matrices. Chemical reduction by ascorbate (Vitamin C), or photosensitized reduction of Fe³⁺-tricarboxylate to Fe²⁺-tricarboxylate crosslinking complexes, yielded a lower-stiffness gel state framework. Concomitant aerobic oxidation of the Fe²⁺-tricarboxylate to the Fe³⁺-tricarboxylate bridging complexes resulted in the dissipative, transient recovery of the parent higher-stiffness gel state. The transient stiffness changes of the bulk matrices were applied for dose-controlled transient release of loads, and as transient chemo/mechanomorphing soft robotic actuation devices.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the transient dissipative Fe^{3+/2+}-crosslinked CMC and its application for transient dissipative release of loads and as a functional soft-robotic actuation unit.

The results were reported in detail in a previous report, and the detailed experimental results and scientific accomplishments were **published as an open-access research paper in *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 146, 9957–9966, 2024**, acknowledging the MAPWORMS European project, 101046846.^[2]

3 CURRENT RESEARCH ACTIVITIES

An update on the research activities and achievements, and the relevance of the research to the MAPWORMS project, is provided.

3.1 SURFACE-IMMOBILIZED COVALENT/REDOX-RESPONSIVE COOPERATIVELY CROSSLINKED GEL FRAMEWORKS, DEMONSTRATING CONTROLLED TRANSIENT STIFFNESS FUNCTIONS, AND THEIR APPLICATIONS

The method described in section 2.2 has been extended to design other transient gel matrices and, in particular, to adopt other methodologies to construct gels with enhanced complexity and functionality. Within these efforts, we used methacrylate-functionalized CMC (**CMC-MA**) as a basic constituent to assemble redox-responsive gels with controlled, switchable, transient stiffness. **Figure 4(A)** depicts the synthesis of the gel through radical polymerization of the methacrylate crosslinking units of the CMC-MA, yielding a covalently crosslinked gel matrix. Subsequent treatment with Fe²⁺-ions under aerobic conditions yielded a higher-stiffness gel state, cooperatively crosslinked by methacrylate covalent bonds and Fe³⁺-tricarboxylate complexes (**Fe³⁺-CMC-MA**). During this gelation process, different loads and/or integrated photosensitizers, such as the algae-derived isolated photosynthetic apparatus system-I (**PS-I**), were immobilized in the gel matrices. Chemical or

photosensitized reduction of the Fe^{3+} -tricarboxylate resulted in a gel of a lower-stiffness state, which, under aerobic conditions, underwent dissipative transient recovery to the higher-stiffness state gel, **Figure 4(B)**. Different fluorophore-labelled loads of different molecular weights, such as dextran, insulin, or anti-vascular endothelial growth factor (anti-VEGF) aptamers, were loaded, and their dose-controlled, transient, dissipative release was demonstrated. **Figure 4(C), Panel I**, exemplifies the dose-controlled release of a tetramethyl rhodamine-dextran (TMR-D) dye, upon treatment with different concentrations of ascorbate, while **Panel II** depicts their dissipative transient release rates (derived from the time-dependent derivative of the TMR-D release curves depicted in **Panel I**).

Figure 4. (A) Schematic assembly of Fe^{3+} -crosslinked CMC-MA gels and their triggered transient transitions between high and low-stiffness states. (B) Rheometry, time-dependent G' -changes corresponding to the transient ascorbate-mediated reduction of the Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA to the Fe^{2+} -CMC-MA gel state, and the aerobic recovery of the Fe^{2+} -CMC-MA to the parent Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA state. While curve (i) demonstrates the ascorbate-triggered reduction of Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA to the Fe^{2+} -CMC-MA state under N_2 , the reduction under aerobic oxidation in the presence of variable ascorbate concentrations is depicted: (ii) 5 mM, (iii) 10 mM, and (iii) 20 mM. (C) Temporal release of TMR-D from the Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA gel under aerobic conditions in the absence of ascorbate (i), or under aerobic conditions in the presence of different concentrations of ascorbate, corresponding to: (ii) 5 mM, (iii) 10 mM, and (iv) 20 mM, and Panel (II), the transient release rate of TMR-D from the gel. (i) Under aerobic conditions in the absence of ascorbate (i), and in the presence of ascorbate: (ii) 5 mM, (iii) 10 mM, and (iv) 20 mM (transient curves correspond to the time-dependent derivative of the curves).

Further **detailed experimental results and scientific accomplishments are anticipated to be published as an open-access research paper**, and will acknowledge the MAPWORMS European project, 101046846.

3.1.1 REDOX-RESPONSIVE TRANSIENT HYDROGEL MICROCAPSULES FOR DIVERSE BIOMEDICAL APPLICATIONS

The radical polymerization process of the transient $\text{Fe}^{3+/2+}$ CMC-MA gels enables, however, the construction of the gel matrix on inorganic core surfaces, such as calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), SiO_2 , or TiO_2 . This method was implemented to develop loaded (loads and integrated PS-I) redox-responsive hydrogel microcapsules for diverse biomedical applications. **Figure 5(A)** outlines the method for preparing these loaded hydrogel microcapsules. By auxiliary chemical or photochemical reduction of the higher-stiffness state Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA to the lower-stiffness Fe^{2+} -CMC-MA state, the dissipative, transient release of loads was demonstrated. Different fluorophore-labelled loads, such as dextran, insulin, and aptamers, were released from the redox-responsive hydrogel microcapsules. **Figure 5(B)** exemplifies light-triggered cyclic, dose-controlled operation of the transient release of TMR-D (**Panel I**), and anti-VEGF aptamer (**Panel II**).

Figure 5. (A) Schematic synthesis of the surface-immobilized loaded hydrogel microcapsules and their transient operation upon ascorbate or light triggers. (B) Panel I – light-induced transient and cyclic release of TMR-D from the hydrogel microcapsules. Panel II – light-induced transient and cyclic release of anti-VEGF aptamer from the hydrogel microcapsules.

The study, including the **detailed experimental results and scientific accomplishments, is anticipated to be published as an open-access research paper**, and will acknowledge the MAPWORMS European project, 101046846.

3.1.2 BULK, SURFACE-CONFINED, REDOX-RESPONSIVE TRANSIENT HYDROGEL FRAMEWORKS FOR MULTIMODAL-TRIGGERS DISSIPATIVE AND MODULATED LOAD-RELEASE

Beyond the immobilization of the dissipative transient gels on inorganic microparticle surfaces, the radical polymerization method of the CMC-MA polymer was adopted for the design of synthetic procedures towards the assembly of the polymers on bulk conductive surfaces for controlled chemical/photochemical, and electrical multimodal control over transient dissipative controlled release of loads. The Fe³⁺-crosslinked CMC-MA has been deposited on Au-coated surfaces following the method displayed in **Figure 6**. The Au-coated surface is reacted with reduced cysteamine (2-aminoethanethiol) **(a)**, to form a monolayer of free amino groups that are further conjugated with CMC-MA through EDC-S-NHS coupling reaction via free carboxylate groups, forming a layer of CMC-MA on the surface, **(b)**. Further incubation with CMC-MA and subsequent radical-initiated (using APS/TEMED redox couple as initiator) polymerization induces the formation of a surface-confined CMC-MA gel **(c)** that is further cooperatively crosslinked with Fe^{3+/2+}-ions **(d)** to form the redox-responsive surface-immobilized Fe^{3+/2+}-CMC-MA. The gel was stable under aerobic conditions at 4 °C for at least 20 days.

Figure 6. Schematic synthesis of the surface-confined redox-responsive transient gel frameworks. (a) Cysteamine monolayer on the Au-coated surface. (b) Surface-coupled CMC-MA layer formation. (c) Surface-confined CMC-MA gel. (d) Formation of Fe³⁺-CMC gel on the surface and its electrochemically-triggered transitions, and a photograph of the deposited gel on Au-coated surface.

Following the development of the synthetic procedure for assembling the gel on the surface, further experiments were performed.

1. The surface-confined gel was loaded with different loads (e.g., TMR-D, Insulin, or aptamers). The gel exhibited transient dissipative stiffness properties upon aerobic chemical reduction of the higher-stiffness Fe³⁺-CMC-MA to the lower-stiffness state Fe²⁺-CMC-MA, while allowing the reoxidation of the Fe²⁺-CMC-MA to the parent higher-stiffness state Fe³⁺-CMC-MA. **Figure 7(A)** exemplifies the ascorbate-induced release of TMR-D (**Panel I**) and the cyclic release of TMR-D (**Panel II**) from the surface-confined matrix.
2. The gel on the conductive Au-coated support exhibited quasi-reversible redox properties. **Figure 7(B), Panel I** depicts the cyclic voltammogram corresponding to the reduction/oxidation of the Fe³⁺/Fe²⁺-redox bridges. The redox responses enabled the transient electrochemically-triggered release of loads incorporated in the gel matrix. For example, upon electrochemical reduction of the Fe³⁺-CMC-MA to the Fe²⁺-CMC-MA by the application of constant potential (-0.210 mV vs. SCE) and subsequently allowed to release the load in the absence of applied potential, under

aerobic conditions. **Figure 7(B), Panel II** depicts the electrochemical release of TMR-D. **(i)** The load release is dependent on the duration of the applied electrochemical pulse to reduce the Fe^{3+} -crosslinking ions to the Fe^{2+} -bridges. **(ii)** The electrochemically triggered release of the loads reveals dissipative transient behaviour. **(iii)** The release process could be cycled and electrically modulated during the transient release process. **(iv)** Control experiments revealed that the Fe^{3+} -crosslinked surface-confined CMC-MA matrix is blocked against the release of the load.

Figure 7. (A) Panel I – ascorbate-induced (20 mM) release of TMR-D from the surface-confined Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA, inset – TMR-D rate of release. Panel II – ascorbate-induced (20 mM) cyclic release of TMR-D, inset – rate of release, derived from the time-dependent release curve. (B) Panel I - cyclic voltammogram of the bare electrode, cysteamine mono-layer modified electrode, and the surface-immobilized $\text{Fe}^{3+/2+}$ -CMC-MA gel. Panel II – electrochemically-induced release of TMR-D from the surface-confined gel corresponding to: (i) Fe^{3+} -crosslinked CMC-MA (blocked configuration) without activation of potential, (ii) after 5 minutes of applied potential, and (iii) after 15 minutes of reducing potential activation.

The following characterization experiments of the systems will be carried out:

- Characterization of the electrochemically triggered transient $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ changes and concomitant stiffness changes of the gel matrices associated with the Au-coated

surfaces by nanoindentation techniques and X-ray photon spectroscopy (XPS) analysis.

- Application of the electrochemical release of loads to other load constituents, e.g., aptamers and proteins.
- The integration of PS-I to hydrogel frameworks associated with the Au-coated surfaces, and probing the light-triggered transient release of the different loads.

These research results basically complete the different deliverables of WP4 by demonstrating the following accomplishments:

- Deliverables 4.1, 4.3 - Introducing the concept of transient stimuli-responsive gel matrices exhibiting dissipative transient stiffness properties as bulk soft materials. These stimuli-responsive transient gels were implemented for transient, controlled load-release, self-healing, and soft-robotic actuation. Different triggers, including chemical agents and light, were used to activate the dynamic transient properties of the different gel matrices.
- Deliverables 4.2, 4.4 - Methods to integrate the transient gels on surface supports were developed. These included the deposition of the gels on loaded microparticle templates and the application of the hybrid system to yield (after an acid-based etching process) redox-responsive transient dissipative hydrogel microcapsule frameworks. Alternatively, the stimuli-responsive gels were deposited on conductive Au-coated surfaces and loaded with different desired loads. Chemical/photochemical/light multimodal-triggered release of the loads from surface-confined matrices was demonstrated.
- The research results have important potential applicative outputs reflected by the possibilities to apply the systems to control the transient load-release for biomedical applications, and for autonomously driven soft-robotic frameworks.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The MAPWORMS project is dedicated to the development of a paradigm-shifting robotic architecture inspired by the physiological mechanisms of marine annelids. By harnessing the synergistic potential of stimuli-responsive, stiffness-switchable gel frameworks, we have engineered discrete activation units capable of complex functions. These units are modulated by a diverse library of external triggers, including chemical, electrochemical,

thermal, and light triggers, thereby emulating the primitive yet highly efficient biological functions of the worm. To bridge the gap between individual actuators and a cohesive robotic organism, these units must be seamlessly integrated within the soft-bodied scaffold. This necessitates immobilizing the hydrogel phase spatially onto functionalized substrates, specifically electroactive surfaces, to maintain structural integrity and facilitate signal transduction. Consequently, Deliverable 4.4 provides a critical update on the fabrication of these surface-tethered stimuli-responsive matrices. Within these efforts, we present a general methodology for the assembly of transient, stiffness-switchable hydrogels on solid-state interfaces, providing the foundational architecture for next-generation soft robotics.

The activities of WP4 within the MAPWORM project addressed the following basic concepts:

- The design of different scientific and technological strategies to design stimuli-responsive gel matrices of switchable and controlled stiffness properties. Within these objectives, the development of various stimuli-responsive triggers, including chemical, biocatalytic, photochemical, and electrochemical triggers, was set as a goal. Moreover, different gel frameworks had to be developed to achieve these goals.
- Beyond the microscopic, spectroscopic, and mechanical detailed characterization of the different stimuli-responsive gel matrices, the project focused on the identification of emerging functions and possible applications of these frameworks. These included their application as switchable, controlled, and temporal release of loads, the use of the stiffness-programmable gels for self-healing applications, and the implementation of their programmed stiffness and functions for autonomous biomimetic soft-robotic actuations.
- The integration of the different stimuli-responsive gel matrices with surfaces as hybrid composites that allow the sequestered synthesis of stimuli-responsive gels in the form of microscale frameworks, and the use of the hybrid conjugates as microdevices that could be remotely activated by auxiliary triggers such as chemicals, light, or voltage.

Our primary activities within the MAPWORMS project included the development of nucleic acid-functionalized hydrogel and cryogel matrices as stimuli-responsive frameworks to reach our goals. Within these efforts, we developed pH-responsive nucleic acid-functionalized hydrogel and cryogel matrices and demonstrated pH-responsive, programmable, and switchable stiffness properties with these matrices, and applied these gels as pH-responsive mechanomorphing soft-robotic systems. Furthermore, we integrated into the pH-responsive gels enzymes (glucose oxidase, GOx) and demonstrated the biocatalyzed temporal stiffness changes and mechano-morphing functions of these matrices.^[3] In addition, we were able to develop a method to assemble pH-responsive

nucleic acid-functionalized hydrogels on Au-coated surfaces, and we demonstrated the electro-driven bioelectrocatalyzed release of loads from these surface-confined hydrogels.^[2] Nevertheless, although these results validated the concept and potential applications of the stimuli-responsive DNA-based gels, we realized the fundamental drawbacks and limitations associated with the need to modify the gels with nucleic acids as constituents. Accordingly, in the second phase of the project, our efforts were directed to overcome these challenges. Indeed, these efforts revolutionized the topic of stimuli-responsive gel matrices. Within these efforts, we introduced a new class of stimuli-responsive gel matrices, namely enzyme-free, dissipative, transient-responsive gel frameworks.^[1] Within 2 years, we highlighted the advances and innovative concepts introduced by this new class of gel matrices. The major accomplishments included:

- The development of a versatile and general methodology to prepare redox-responsive $\text{Fe}^{3+/2+}$ -crosslinked polysaccharide gel matrices. The reduction of the Fe^{3+} -crosslinked state, which exhibited higher stiffness than the lower-stiffness Fe^{2+} -crosslinked state, and aerobic oxidation of the Fe^{2+} -crosslinked state led to transient stiffness of the gel frameworks. A variety of microscopic, spectroscopic, and mechanical characterization methods were developed to characterize the temporal behavior of these matrices.
- Diverse chemical, photochemical, and electrochemical methods to trigger and operate the transient stiffness properties of the gels were developed.
- These gels were assembled as bulk (macroscopic) matrices or as microscale hydrogel microcapsule assemblies and were successfully deposited on surfaces.
- Diverse applications of the transient gel frameworks were accomplished, including their use as matrices for transient controlled load-release and self-healing matrices for biomedical applications. Moreover, these matrices provided versatile means for developing stimuli-responsive, autonomous soft-robotic devices.

These results will be reported in a set of forthcoming scientific publications acknowledging the MAPWORMS European project, 101046846.

We believe that the research activities in this part of the MAPWORM project have established a new field in stimuli-responsive gel frameworks that will certainly find broad applications across disciplines, including medicine, agriculture, catalysis, food science, environmental management, and soft-robotics.

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